

MULTIFUNCTIONAL GRAPHENE-BASED NANOCOMPOSITES WITH SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS OF CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL INTERACTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Here in, polyamide 66 nanocomposites with graphene-based nanofillers were prepared and the structure and the properties were investigated. In order to achieve the high dispersibility of the nanofillers, the nanocomposites were prepared by in-situ polymerization. As graphene-based nanofillers, graphene oxide and the chemically modified GO were used. It was revealed that the mechanical properties and the thermal properties significantly increased by the incorporation of graphene-based nanofillers. The nanocomposites with chemically modified GO showed higher Young's modulus, tensile strength and thermal properties. These results indicates that the synergistic effects of chemical and physical interfacial interactions in the nanocomposites achieved the excellent reinforcement effects.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the first development of polymer nanocomposites by Toyota Central R&D Labs., Inc., research on polymer nanocomposites has intensively been conducted for various applications. So far, many types of nanomaterials have been investigated as nanofillers for polymer nanocomposites, such as nanocarbons, nitride compounds, nanofibers and so on. Among them, nanofillers with high aspect ratio have been revealed to show excellent reinforcement effect to achieve the significant improvement in the properties of polymer materials. Graphene is a single layer of graphite with one-atom-thickness and has high aspect ratio. Graphene have attracted great attention because of its excellent mechanical properties, thermal properties, electrical properties and so on since Geim et al. won the Nobel Prize in physics for discovering and identifying its unique properties.

In this study, graphene-based polyamide 66 (PA66) nanocomposites were prepared by in-situ polymerization. In the process of in-situ polymerization, polymerization proceeded under the presence of fillers. Therefore, the dispersibility of a filler in a solvent can be maintained even in the nanocomposites. In addition, fillers can chemically react with polymer matrices during the polymerization, resulting in the strong interfacial interactions through covalent bonds. We used two types of graphene, graphene oxide (GO) and the chemically modified GO (GO-DDA) and investigated the effect of the surface functional groups of graphene oxide (GO) and the chemically modified GO (GO-DDA) on the structure and the properties of the nanocomposites.

2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

GO aqueous suspension or GO-DDA was dispersed in pure water. The amount of filler was controlled to be 0.1 wt% in the suspension. The suspension was ultrasonicated for 90 min in water bath to obtain the high exfoliation of GO or GO-DDA. The GO or GO-DDA suspension was added to the mixture of hexamethylenediamine and sodium hydroxide solution and then stirred for 1 h (mixture 1). The organic chloride mixture which contained adipoyl chloride and carbon tetrachloride (mixture 2) was prepared in the other beaker. The mixture 1 was slowly added to the top of the mixture 2 using a glass rod. The condensation polymerization of PA66 was proceeded at the interface between mixture 1 and mixture 2

under the presence of GO or GO-DDA. The reaction product was wound on the glass rod, followed by washing with water and ethanol for several times. For the purification, re-precipitation with phenol and methanol was carried out to remove the unreacted solvents and low-molecular-weight products. After vacuum filtration, the product was washed with water, dried at 40 °C for 48 h and then in vacuum at 40 °C for 72 h. The dried product was put between aluminum plates with a spacer and then melt pressed at 270 °C to obtain the PA66/GO nanocomposite or PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposite with a thickness of 0.2 mm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 Optical images of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites.

Figure 2 UV-vis spectra of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites.

Figure 1 and Figure 2 shows the optical images and UV-vis spectra of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites, respectively. The nanocomposites exhibited the favorable transparency, indicating the homogeneous dispersion of the fillers. Compared to the nanocomposites with GO, the nanocomposites with GO-DDA shows higher transparency. It was suggested that the dispersibility in PA66 was improved by the chemical modification of GO.

Figure 3 SEM images of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites (0.5 wt%) and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites (0.5 wt%).

Figure 3 shows SEM images of the cross section of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites. The filler content was 0.5 wt%. It was revealed that the fillers were homogeneously dispersed and highly aligned in the in-plane direction of the nanocomposites.

Figure 4 shows XRD profiles of PA 66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites. All the profiles show the characteristic peaks of (100) and (010)/(110) of PA66 at 2 theta of 20.9 ° and 24.2 °, respectively. Since there is no shift in peak position, there is no change in d-spacing by the addition of GO or GO-DDA. The crystallinity estimated from the profiles are inserted in Figure 4. The crystallinity of the nanocomposites increases with the addition of GO or GO-DDA. It is well known that nanofillers can act as crystallization nuclei in polymer nanocomposites. At the same time, nanofillers can increase the viscosity of composite suspensions/solutions and cause the low molecular mobility which decrease the crystallinity. These counter effects can also occur in PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites. It is assumed that the former effect might be slightly dominant in the present nanocomposites.

Figure 4 X-ray diffraction profiles of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites.

Figure 5 ATR-FTIR spectra of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites.

Figure 5 shows the ATR-FTIR spectra of PA66, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites. The characteristic bands derive from amide bonds in PA66 are observed for all the spectra. Both of the bands at 3385 cm^{-1} and 3305 cm^{-1} are attributed to N-H stretching vibration, while the lower wavenumber indicates the effects of intermolecular or intramolecular hydrogen bonds of PA66. The intensity of the bands at 3305 cm^{-1} of the PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites is weaker than that of the PA66/GO nanocomposites, indicating the decrease of hydrogen bonds due to the substitution of carboxy groups to DDA on GO surface. Furthermore, the PA66/GO nanocomposite had the highest amide bond content, followed in the order of PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites > PA66. It is revealed that the formation of amide bonds is facilitated in the process of the *in-situ* polymerization of the nanocomposites.

Figure 6 Stress-strain curves of (A) PA66/GO nanocomposites and (B) PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites

Figure 6 shows stress-strain curves of (A) PA66/GO nanocomposites and (B) PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites. It was revealed that the Young's modulus increased by 75% and 100% by the addition of 0.5 wt% of GO and GO-DDA, respectively. The strong reinforcement effects of the fillers were successfully imparted to the nanocomposites by the strong interfacial interactions and the high dispersibility with in-plane alignment. From the theoretical analysis using Halpin-Tsai model, the Young's modulus of the PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites was revealed to be higher than that of the theoretical value at all the filler content. It was assumed that the physical interactions between PA66 and DDA molecular chains on GO-DDA played the important role in the reinforcement of the nanocomposites.

As for the thermal properties, the nanocomposites showed excellent thermal resistance. For example, the thermal decomposition temperature increased by 26 °C and 31 °C by the addition of 0.5 wt% of GO and GO-DDA, respectively. The molecular motion of PA66 was restricted by the highly dispersed/aligned fillers with strong interfacial interactions. In addition, generation of volatile decomposition products were effectively barriered by the 2D fillers aligned to the in-plane direction.

In conclusion, the synergistic effects of chemical and physical interfacial interactions of the graphene-based nanocomposites lead the superior reinforcement effect in the mechanical and thermal properties at low content.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites were prepared by in-situ polymerization. As a result, the high dispersibility with in-plane alignment of the fillers was achieved in the nanocomposites. The crystallinity increase by the incorporation of GO or GO-DDA, indicating the nucleation effects by these nanofillers. ATR-FTIR spectra indicate that amide bonds are formed at the interfaces between PA66 and the fillers for both PA66/GO nanocomposites and PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites. The excellent reinforcement effects on the mechanical and thermal properties are revealed. Compared to PA66, the Young's modulus increases by 92% for the nanocomposites at only 0.3 wt% loading of GO-DDA, while it increases by 42% for the nanocomposites with GO at the same content. In addition, the thermal decomposition temperature of the PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposite at 0.3 wt% is 31 °C higher than that of PA66. It is assumed that the synergetic effect of chemical and physical interfacial interactions lead the superior reinforcement effects of the PA66/GO-DDA nanocomposites at low content.